

JAHON IQTISODIY INQIROZI DAVRIDA KANADA IQTISODIYOTI

Srojeva Gulbahor Vahobovna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

Tarix va filologiya kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

gulbahorsrojeva@gmail.com

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Annotatsiya. 1933 yilning birinchi choragida asosiy ko'rsatkichlarning eng past darajalari va iqtisodiyotning tadbirkorlik faoliyati, ishlab chiqarish va ishlab chiqarishning jismoniy hajmi, eksport va import hajmi, ulgurji narxlar va universal do'konlarning chakana savdosi pasayishi kuzatildi. Yangi investitsiyalar egri chizig'i davom etdi. 1933 yil o'rtalariga qadar pasaydi va keyinchalik bu o'sish shunchalik ahamiyatsiz ediki, yillik ko'rsatkich 1932 yilga nisbatan past bo'ldi. 1933 yilning ikkinchi choragida bandlikning eng yuqori darajasi qayd etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kanada, Jahon iqtisodiy inqirozi, xom ashyo, yarim tayyor mahsulotlar, burjuaziya, fond birja.

THE CANADIAN ECONOMY DURING THE GLOBAL ECONOMIC CRISIS

Abstract. In the first quarter of 1933, the lowest levels of the main indicators and the entrepreneurial activity of the economy, the physical volume of production and production, the volume of exports and imports, wholesale prices and retail sales of department stores were observed. The curve of new investments continued. It declined until the middle of 1933, and thereafter the increase was so insignificant that the annual figure was lower than that of 1932. The highest level of employment was recorded in the second quarter of 1933.

Key words: Canada, World economic crisis, raw materials, semi-finished products, bourgeoisie, stock exchange.

КАНАДСКАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА ВО ВРЕМЯ МИРОВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО КРИЗИСА

Аннотация. В первом квартале 1933 года наблюдались самые низкие уровни основных показателей и предпринимательской активности экономики, физического объема производства и производства, объема экспорта и импорта, оптовых цен и розничной торговли универмагов. Кривая новых инвестиций продолжала Оно снижалось до середины 1933 года, а затем прирост был настолько незначительным, что годовой показатель оказался ниже, чем в 1932 году. Самый высокий уровень занятости был зафиксирован во втором квартале 1933 года.

Ключевые слова: Канада, Мировой экономический кризис, сырье, полуфабрикаты, буржуазия, фондовая биржа.

Jahon kapital bozoriga asosiy xom ashyo va yarim tayyor mahsulotlar yetkazib beruvchi Kanadaning o'ziga xos vaziyati tufayli 20-yillarning oxirida jahon almashinuvining buzilishi va tabiiy ofatlar mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga ayniqsa noqulay ta'sir ko'rsatdi. . So'nggi yillarda ishlab chiqarishning sustlashuvi ko'lami bo'yicha va inqirozning halokatliligi nuqtai nazaridan Kanada jahon iqtisodiy inqirozining markazi sifatida AQShdan ancha orqada edi.

Turg'unlikning aniq belgilari 1928 yildayoq o'zini ko'rsatdi, ammo ular Kanadadagi biznes va siyosiy soha vakillari tomonidan e'tiborga olinmadi. Ular 1929-yil oxirida avjiga chiqqan

qimmatli qog'ozlar va qimmatli qog'ozlar bo'yicha chayqovchilik orgiyasidan ham xavotirga tushishmadi. Hatto 1929-yilning oktabr va noyabr oylarida Nyu York fond birjasida, shuningdek, Monreal va Toronto fond birjalarida millionlab aksiyalarning vahima sotilishi ham ularni tashvishga solmadi. , Kanada burjuaziyasi o'rtasida dastlabki uch yeti yillikda ildiz otgan "iqtisodiy haddan tashqari yaqinlik va abadiy "farovonlik" illyuziyasini silkitish uchun mo'ljallangan edi. XX asr qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorining qulashi dastlab shunchaki spekulyativ bum (chayqovchi urilish portlash) natijasida qimmatli qog'ozlar narxining pasayishiga "texnik tuzatish" sifatida qaraldi.

Kanada Bankirlar Assotsiatsiyasi 1930 yil yanvar oyida aksiyalarning qadrsizlanishi tendentsiyasini e'tiborsiz qoldirib, umumiy indeks, ishbilarmonlik faolligining biroz pasayishiga e'tiborsiz qaradi. Bu takabburlik ham xarakterli edi. mamlakatning siyosiy rahbarlari, shu jumladan Kanada hukumati rahbari Liberal Bosh vazir King. o'z kundaligida 1929 yilning oxirigacha har kuni juda ko'p mayda narsalarni, shu jumladan uning qarorgohidagi Puare Hakayadagi yotoqxonaning devorlari boshqa rangga bo'yalganligi, Klemenso vafot etgani va hokazolarni qayd etgan. uning uzun yozuvlarida birja fondi haqida esa hech qanday gap yo'q

Bir necha oydan beri xavotirli signal berib, iqtisodiy jihatdan qichqira boshlagan.

1930 yil bahorida parlament sessiyasi mamlakatni 1929 yil oxiridagi tanazzuldan so'ng Kanada yaxshi davrlarga qaytganiga ishontirishga harakat qildi. Hatto 1920 yil iyun oyida kapital sanoatchilarning yog'och zavodi prezidenti sessiyada yaxshilanishning ba'zi jonli bo'lmagan belgilari allaqachon mavjudligini ta'kidlashga jur'at etdi.

Ko'p jihatdan eksportga yo'naltirilgan Kanada iqtisodiyoti uchun jahon narxlari strukturasi yo'q qilish halokatli oqibatlariga olib keladi. 1929 yildan boshlab barcha iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar qor to'pi kabi pastga tushdi. 1933 yil boshiga kelib sanoat ishlab chiqarishi ikki baravar, bandlik uchdan bir qismga qisqardi, ishsizlik 700 ming kishidan oshdi. Dashtlardagi chang bo'ronlari quyoshni ko'mib, tabiatning o'z-o'zidan paydo bo'lgan g'alayonini iqtisodiy inqirozning barham topishi bilan birlashtirdi

Sanoat aholini ro'yxatga olish ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 1932 yil boshida sanoat ishlab chiqarish quvvatlaridan foydalanish proteksionizm bilan himoyalangan mashinasozlikda 25% dan to'qimachilik sanoatida 70% gacha o'zgarib turardi. Po'lat sanoati ishlab chiqarishni 1920 yil darajasidan 10% gacha, avtomobil ishlab chiqarishni 16 taga, harakat tarkibi zavodlari va quyish zavodlari 25% gacha qisqartirdi.

1933 yilning birinchi choragida asosiy ko'rsatkichlarning eng past darajalari va iqtisodiyotning tadbirkorlik faoliyati, ishlab chiqarish va ishlab chiqarishning jismoniy hajmi, eksport va import hajmi, ulgurji narxlar va universal do'konlarning chakana savdosi pasayishi kuzatildi. Yangi investitsiyalar egri chizig'i davom etdi. 1933 yil o'rtalariga qadar pasaydi va keyinchalik bu o'sish shunchalik ahamiyatsiz ediki, yillik ko'rsatkich 1932 yilga nisbatan past bo'ldi. 1933 yilning ikkinchi choragida bandlikning eng yuqori darajasi qayd etildi.

Xodimlar soni taxminan bir xil darajada saqlanib qoldi va ularning o'rtacha ish haqi deyarli 10% ga kamaydi. Ishchilar soni 45 foizga, ish haqi esa o'rtacha 15 foizga kamaydi. Shubhasiz, mehnatning intensivlashuvi ortdi. Agar 1929 yilda ishlab chiqarish sanoatida bir ishchiga o'rtacha 3 ming ulush nisbatan sof mahsulot (qo'shilgan qiymat) to'g'ri kelgan bo'lsa, 1932 yilda u allaqachon 3430 dollarni tashkil etdi.

1937 yilgacha asosiy fondlarga yangi xususiy investitsiyalar amortizatsiyani qoplamadi. Inqiroz asosiy kapitalni takror ishlab chiqarish jarayonini chuqur izdan chiqardi va bu jarayon Ikkinchi jahon urushi boshlanishiga qadar hech qachon normal holatga qaytmadi.

Zararli tarmoqlardan kapitalni o'tkazish bir qancha sabablarga ko'ra qiyin bo'lgan, ulardan eng muhimi Kanadaning xorijiy kapitalga qattiq qaramligi edi. 1930 yilda Kanada biznesiga va davlat obligatsiyalariga qo'yilgan barcha investitsiyalarning 40% ga yaqini u yoki bu shaklda xorijiy mulkdorlarga tegishli edi. 1928-1929 yillarda Tashqi qarz majburiyatlari va xorijiy aktsiyadorlarning dividendlari eksport va xizmatlardan tushgan barcha tushumlarning 1% ni va 1932-1933 yillarda o'zlashtirildi. "Qayta kapitallashuv" hodisasi ayniqsa yaqqol namoyon bo'lgan eksport tarmoqlarida xorijiy kapitalning muhim roli kapitalning boshqa tarmoqlarga harakatini deyarli istisno qildi. "Eksport tarmoqlaridagi katta miqdordagi kapitalni boshqa sohalarga aylantirib bo'lmaydi", - deyiladi qirollik komissiyasining federal-viloyat munosabatlari bo'yicha hisobotida."

Inqiroz yillarida ishchilar sinfi, dehqonlar va o'rta qatlamlar ommasining iste'moli keskin qisqardi. Ichki bozorga xizmat ko'rsatuvchi barcha tarmoqlarda eksport tarmoqlari kabi ishlab chiqarish va aholi bandligining deyarli bir xil qisqarishi kuzatildi. 1930 yilda AQShda qabul qilingan va Kanada iqtisodiyotining qishloq xo'jaligi va eksport tarmoqlariga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan proteksionistik Xouli-Smoot tarifiga, shuningdek, 1932 yilda Kanadadan AQShga olib kelingan yog'och va misga qo'shimcha bojlarning kiritilishiga qarshi chiqdi. o'z navbatida Kanada hukumati proteksionizmni kuchaytirdi. Bu burjuaziya va sanoatchilarning ichki bozorga yo'naltirilgan qismining manfaatlariga javob berdi.

Proteksionizmning kuchayishi Kanada burjuaziyasi uchun bir qator kutilmagan oqibatlarga olib keldi, ulardan asosiysi Amerika kapitalining kengayishining o'sishi (asosan, mamlakatda qolgan Amerika kompaniyalarining daromadlarini investitsiya qilish shaklida). Bu yillar davomida u unchalik yangi loyihalar yaratmadi

Kichik ishlab chiqarish va metall ishlab chiqarishni ekspropriatsiya qilish tizimida metan fikr uyasi muhim o'rin egalladi. Inqirozning eng past nuqtasida monopoliya maqsadlari 1925 yil darajasining atigi 87 foizida ishlaydi; yaqinda kartel kelishuvlari narxlarni 81 foizdan pastga tushirdi. Va shu bilan birga, raqobat sharoitida shakllangan jarimalar (2-hozirgi qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari bozoridagi narxlarda 48,4% darajasiga. L. Bu sakrashda, tizim monopol jazolar inqirozdan chiqish vaqtini qiyinlashtirdi va kechiktirdi".

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